

GOUT AND ITS ASSOCIATION WITH BIOCHEMICAL MARKERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14173037>

Introduction: Gout is a metabolic condition characterized by elevated levels of uric acid, which forms crystals that affect the joints and can lead to kidney damage. Gouty nephropathy, a serious complication, refers to kidney impairment in individuals with chronic gout. This thesis examines the relationship between gout, biochemical markers, and the development of gouty nephropathy, particularly focusing on serum creatinine and uric acid levels.

Data: 1. Patients: A total of 46 patients diagnosed with gout, including 3 females and 44 males.

2. Age Range: The patients' ages ranged between 40 and 70 years.

3. Gouty Nephropathy: Among the 46 patients, 20 males had been diagnosed with gouty nephropathy, with 15 of them aged over 50.

4. Biochemical Analysis Results: Creatinine Levels: 20 patients had serum creatinine levels above 130 mmol/l (normal creatinine levels for males: 62-106 mmol/l, females: 53-97 mmol/l).

Uric Acid Levels: All patients had elevated uric acid levels, confirming the diagnosis of gout.

Patients over 50 years old: For those aged over 50, serum creatinine levels were higher than 130 mmol/l, and uric acid levels exceeded 7 mg/dl (normal uric acid levels for men: 3.5-7.2 mg/dl, women: 2.6-6.0 mg/dl).

Analysis: Creatinine Levels: Elevated creatinine levels indicate potential kidney dysfunction. In patients over 50, the high creatinine levels suggest a greater risk of gouty nephropathy. Regular monitoring of serum creatinine is essential for assessing kidney health in gout patients.

Uric Acid Levels: Elevated uric acid levels are characteristic of gout and contribute to the formation of crystals in the kidneys and joints. In patients over 50, the higher uric acid levels indicate more severe progression of gout and an increased risk of nephropathy.

Clinical Implications: The relationship between age and biochemical markers shows that gout and gouty nephropathy are more prevalent in older patients, making early detection and management crucial to prevent further complications.

Conclusion: Elevated creatinine and uric acid levels are significant biochemical indicators of gout and its complications, including gouty nephropathy. Patients

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aged over 50 are at higher risk of kidney damage and need regular monitoring of these markers. Early detection and appropriate treatment are key to improving patient outcomes.